

SYNTHETIC APPROACHES TOWARDS TRITERPENES

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Methods for the preparation of a phenanthrenoid hydrocarbon with two vicinal angular methyl groups and of a similar phenanthrenoid ketone have been established. Preparation of two isomeric keto-octalenes has also been described.

Triterpenes like β -amyrin, oleanolic acid, etc. form a very important group of plant products. Synthetic approaches in this group have been mostly confined to the synthesis of the dehydrogenation products of these compounds.

The most conspicuous part of the ring structure of a triterpene like oleanolic acid (I) is the hydrogenated phenanthrene skeleton (rings B, C and D) with two vicinal angular methyl groups, No. 26 and 27 in positions 9 and 14 in the central part of the molecule.

In this paper, as a preliminary measure, three different routes for the synthesis of a hydrophenanthrene structure of the type (II) with two vicinal angular methyl groups No. 15 and 16 in positions 11 and 12 of the hydrophenanthrene ring-structure have been described.

Route I: Dimethoxybenzoin, (IV), prepared from *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (III) according to Irvine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 668), on the Clemmensen reduction or catalytic hydrogenation was converted in good yield into 2:2'-dimethoxy-1:2-diphenylethane (V), this method of preparation being far superior to the methods described by earlier workers (Irvine and Moodie, *ibid.*, 1907, 91, 54); demethylation with pyridine hydrochloride (Mason, *ibid.*, 1947, 251) afforded the corresponding diphenolic compound, 2:2'-dihydroxy-1:2-diphenylethane (VI). The dinitrodiphenylethane derivative (XIV), prepared from *o*-nitrotoluene (XII) and ethyl formate (Lapworth, *ibid.*, 1901, 79, 1275), on hydrogenation to the diamino compound (XV), followed by diazotisation and heating, also furnished the same diphenolic compound (VI) in satisfactory yield. On hydrogenation under pressure (VI) was converted into the crystalline diol (VII), which on oxidation with chromic acid afforded the solid diketone (VIII). The

latter reacted with two moles of magnesiummethyl iodide to form the crystalline ditertiary alcohol (IX), which in the next stage, through cyclodehydration with phosphoric acid (Linstead, *ibid.*, 1936, 470, 477), was converted into the desired phenanthrenoid compound, **11:12-dimethyl- $\Delta^{3:4}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene (XI)**, formed, presumably, through the intermediate diene (X). The yields in all the stages were excellent, being almost quantitative or nearly so. The cyclic structure of (XI) was proved as, (i) it absorbed one mole of hydrogen, indicating the presence of one double bond, and (ii) dehydrogenation with selenium produced phenanthrene. The position of the double bond in (XI) is provisional.

Route II: This route has not been worked out in all the details as in the case of route I. In certain stages the intermediates were not isolated in analytically pure

state. However, the ultimate phenanthrene derivative (XI) and the diene (X) could be successfully prepared by this method also, the actual isolation of the diene (X) in this case being possible. The acetate (XVIII) of the keto-alcohol (XVII), prepared from cyclohexanone and formaldehyde (Bodendorf, *Ber.*, 1943, 76, 641), on reaction with one mole of magnesiummethyl iodide, keto-group reacting preferentially, formed the tertiary alcohol (XIX); dehydration, followed by hydrolysis, furnished α -methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl carbinol (XXI). The bromide (XXII) of this allylic alcohol was converted into the diene (X) by treatment with sodium, as in the case of the preparation of diallyl (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1941, p. 453); cyclisation with phosphoric acid afforded the same phenanthrenoid compound (XI).

Route III: By this route, which has no relationship to the two earlier routes, a hydrophenanthrenoid ketone (XXVI or XXVII) was obtained by condensing methylacetylcyclohexene (XXIII) with *O*-methylcyclohexanone (XXIV) following the method of Huber as employed in a different preparation (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 725). In this reaction, presumably an open-chain unsaturated ketone (XXV) was formed as an intermediate product.

It showed the typical absorption spectra of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone, which confirmed its cyclic structure. For various reasons, the confirmation of one of the structures by conversion into phenanthrene (XXVIII) or methylphenanthrene (XXIX) through dehydrogenation has not been carried out so far.

Miscellaneous approaches: Apart from the routes mentioned above, a few other interesting approaches were also made, though the results were not always positive. Unsuccessful attempts were made to prepare the diketone (VIII) by condensing ethylene dibromide in one or two stages with cyclohexanone or cyclohexanone carboxylic ester in presence of sodium ethoxide or sodamide (Haller and Cornubert, *Compt. rend.*, 1913, 186, 1199) as employed in other preparations, but instead, only

*cyclohexylidene*cyclohexanone was obtained. In another experiment, β -cyclohexanonyl alcohol was obtained by hydrolysing the condensation product of cyclohexanone carboxylic ester with β -chloroethylacetate, but in view of the unsatisfactory yield, it was not further processed to (VIII).

Finally, in another interesting series of experiments methiodide of the Mannich base (XXX), obtained from cyclohexanone (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 355), was condensed with β -ketovaleric ester (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53) to produce a mixture of two isomeric, hitherto unknown, $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones, 2-keto-1-methyl- $\Delta^{1:9}$ -octalenes (XXXI and XXXII), which could be separated through their semicarbazones or through their differential reactivity towards magnesiummethyl iodide, as the keto group present in one of these was quite resistant towards Grignard's reagent. In next stage, attempt was made to prepare the dimethyldecalone derivative (XXXIII) *via* the method of β -alkylation in presence of magnesiummethyl iodide and cuprous bromide (Birch and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1943, 501). This was to be converted in subsequent stages into a suitable phenanthrenoid derivative, but instead of the desired compound (XXXIII), the tertiary alcohol, (XXXIV), was obtained as the sole product.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Dimethoxybenzoin (IV) was prepared from *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde according to the method of Irvine (*loc. cit.*), and crystallised from a large volume of ether, m.p. 101°.

2:2'-Dimethoxy-1:2-diphenylethane (V).—The dimethoxybenzoin (35 g.) was reduced by refluxing with mechanical stirring in a three-necked flask with zinc-amalgam (100 g.) and HCl (conc., 400 c.c., 1:1), a slow current of HCl being passed through the reaction mixture. The reaction lasted for about 12 hours when most of the amalgam had gone into solution. After cooling, the reduction product was extracted with ether, washed, dried (Na_2SO_4) and after removal of the solvent it was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether. A second crop was obtained by distilling the mother-liquor ($160^\circ\text{--}180^\circ/3$ mm.) followed by crystallisation; total yield 27.5 g., m.p. 84° (Irviñe, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. $83\text{--}84^\circ$).

Working on a small scale (1 g.), it was found that the reduction could be carried out catalytically ($\text{PtO}_2\text{--EtOH}$) and crystallising the product in the usual way, m.p. 84° , yield 0.5 g.

2:2'-Dihydroxy-1:2-diphenylethane (VI).—The above compound (V: 16 g.) and anhydrous pyridine hydrochloride (40 g.) were heated at $180^\circ\text{--}200^\circ$ for 3 hours with mechanical stirring in a two necked flask fitted with a condenser and a guard tube. The contents after cooling were diluted with water (200 c.c.) when the dihydroxy compound separated as a sticky gum. The gum was dissolved in a known amount of NaOH solution, filtered, and then slowly poured into boiling water (2.5 litres) containing requisite amount of HCl to make the total mixture slightly acidic. It was boiled for 5 to 10 minutes (charcoal, 5 g.) and filtered hot. On keeping overnight the dihydroxy compound separated in the form of fine needles. It was collected by filtration and washed with a little cold water. The mother-liquor on concentration and cooling furnished a second crop of crystals; total yield 10-11 g. A small sample was recrystallised from hot water, m.p. 114° (Thiele, *Annalen*, 1899, 305, 97, records m.p. 115°). Crystallisation could also be carried out from dilute alcohol.

Preparation of (VI) from o-Nitrotoluene.—2:2'-Dinitro-1:2-diphenylethane (XIV) was prepared according to Lapworth (*loc. cit.*). NaOEt (anhyd., 54 g.), o-nitrotoluene (137 g.) and ethyl formate (74 g.) afforded the crystalline dinitro compound (23 g.), m.p. 121° (Lapworth, m.p. 121°). On catalytic hydrogenation (Raney nickel, 100° , 100 atmosphere) it was quantitatively reduced to the diamino compound (XV), m.p. 75° (Durland and Adkins, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 75°); acetate, m.p. 249° (Thiele *loc. cit.*, m.p. $249\text{--}50^\circ$). The diamino compound (5 g.) was then dissolved in HCl (400 c.c. of water and 6 c.c. of conc. acid) and diazotised in the usual way with ice-cooling with addition of sodium nitrite (4 g.), dissolved in a little water. The reaction mixture was then slowly warmed and finally boiled for 15 minutes. Any hydrocarbon formed was removed by a powerful jet of steam. The aqueous solution on cooling deposited crystals of (VI), m.p. 114° , yield 3 g.

2:2'-Dihydroxy-1:2-dicyclohexylethane (VII).—The diphenolic compound (VI: 23 g.) on catalytic hydrogenation (150° , 100 atmospheres) in presence of Raney nickel in methanolic solution for 10 hours furnished a quantitative yield (24 g.) of (VII) as a viscous mass which could be crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 139° . (Found: C, 74.28; H, 11.7. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 74.28; H, 11.6 per cent).

2:2'-Diketo-1:2-dicyclohexylethane (VIII).—The above diol (20 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) was oxidised by gradual addition of chromic acid (13.3 g. CrO_3 , water 20 c.c., glacial acetic acid 60 c.c.) under cooling. The mixture was left at room temperature for 20 minutes and then warmed on the water-bath for another 20 minutes. After addition of water (300 c.c.), the diketo compound was extracted with ether, washed with bicarbonate, water and then dried. The diketo compound (19 g.), left after removal of the solvent, was as such sufficiently pure, but it was further purified by converting it into the disemicarbazone with semicarbazide hydrochloride (25 g.), sodium acetate (40 g.) and requisite amounts of water and alcohol. The yield of the semicarbazone was very satisfactory (25 g.), m.p. 212° . Due to its extremely insoluble nature it was very difficult to crystallise it from alcohol and it therefore showed a little low nitrogen content. (Found: C, 56.9; H, 8.2; N, 23.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{N}_6$ requires C, 57.1; H, 8.4; N, 25.0 per cent). However, as further purification was not necessary for the next step, it was not attempted. For isolation of the pure diketone, the semicarbazone (25 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 20 minutes with N-HCl (400 c.c.) and the liberated diketone extracted with ether and worked up in the usual way. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 84° . The substance sublimed easily. (Found in a sample dried at $50^\circ/2$ mm. for 2 hours: C, 75.9; H, 9.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.6; H, 9.9 per cent).

2:2'-Dihydroxy-2:2'-dimethyl-1:2-dicyclohexylethane (IX).—To the Grignard solution, prepared from methyl iodide (22 g.), magnesium (4 g.) and ether (150 c.c.), a solution of the above diketone (obtained by decomposition of the semicarbazone, 24 g., and employed as such without crystallisation) in ether (100 c.c.) was added with mechanical stirring (stirring continued for 10 hours) after which the mixture was heated on the water-bath for another 3 hours and then left at room temperature for a further period of 48 hours. After decomposition of the Grignard complex with ammonium chloride and dilute HCl , the ditertiary alcohol was extracted with ether, washed with 2*N*-thiosulphate, water and dried. The yield of the diol after removal of the solvent was quantitative. It could be crystallised from dilute acetone or alcohol, m.p. 114° (unsharp). (Found in a sample dried at $80^\circ/1-2$ mm: C, 75.4; H, 11.8. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.53; H, 11.9 per cent).

11:12-Dimethyl- $\Delta^{3,4}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene (XI).—The above ditertiary alcohol (13 g.) was mixed with syrupy phosphoric acid (100 c.c., d 1.75) and heated at $150^\circ-170^\circ$ with mechanical stirring for 2 to 3 hours. The mixture after cooling and dilution with water was extracted thoroughly with benzene, washed with bicarbonate, water and dried. The residual oil left after removal of the solvent distilled at $105^\circ-110^\circ/0.8$ mm. For purification it was heated over sodium (5 g.) at 180° under slightly reduced pressure for several hours and distilled; it was finally distilled twice over fresh sodium, b.p. $108^\circ/0.5-0.8$ mm., yield 7 g. (viscous oil); n_D^{25} , 1.5236. (Found: C, 88.0; H, 12.01. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}$ requires C, 88.0; H, 12.0 per cent).

Catalytic Hydrogenation.—The hydrocarbon (1.0522 g.) in methanol (150 c.c., containing 0.1 c.c. of conc. HCl .) in presence of Adam's platinum oxidé catalyst (0.102 g.) on complete hydrogenation (4 hours) absorbed 103.4 c.c. of hydrogen; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}$ $\sqrt{1}$ requires 108.2 c.c.

Dehydrogenation and Isolation of Phenanthrene.—The hydrophenanthrene (4 g.) with selenium (8 g.) was heated in a metal bath (350°-400°) for 48 hours. The dehydrogenation product was isolated by extraction of the powdered reaction mixture and the flask with ether in the usual way; the ether was removed and the residue distilled from a micro-retort; yield 2.3 g., b.p. 120°/ (bath temp.) 10⁻⁴ mm. A part of the distillate on three crystallisations from alcohol furnished pure phenanthrene, m.p. 99-100° (mixed m.p.). Another part was converted into the picrate which was crystallised three times from methanol, m.p. 144° (mixed m.p.).

2-Ketocyclohexyl carbinol (XVII) was prepared according to the method of Bodendorf (*loc. cit.*) using barium hydroxide as the condensing agent. *cyclo-Hexanone* (55 g.) and formalin (33 c.c.) afforded the carbinol (14 g.), b.p. 107°/10 mm. The acetate (XVIII) was prepared by acetylating the above carbinol (10 g.) with pyridine (20 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 g.) in the usual way at room temperature; yield 10 g., b.p. 134°/15 mm.

2-Hydroxy-2-methylcyclohexyl carbinol acetate (XIX) was prepared by dropwise addition of the Grignard solution, prepared from methyl iodide (52 g.), magnesium (9.4 g.) and ether (200 c.c.) in the conventional way at 0°, to a solution of the acetoxy compound (XVIII: 55 g.) in ether (400 c.c.) with mechanical stirring; stirring was continued for another 3 hours at 0°, and for 48 hours at room temperature. The Grignard complex was decomposed with ammonium chloride and HCl and the product (XIX) after isolation with ether was purified by distillation through a small column; yield 47 g., b.p. 92-95°/1 mm. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 9.5. C₁₀H₁₈O₂ requires C, 64.5; H, 9.74 per cent).

2-Methyl-Δ¹-cyclohexenyl Carbinol (XXI).—Phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.) was gradually added with mechanical stirring at room temperature to a solution of the acetate (XIX: 31 g.) in dry benzene (400 c.c.) contained in a three-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser and guard tube. Stirring was continued for 5 hours, after which the reaction mixture was heated on the water-bath for another hour. The benzene solution was then removed by decantation, and the phosphoric acid residue washed with fresh benzene. The combined benzene extract was washed, dried and worked up in the usual way. The residual oil after removal of the benzene was dissolved in methanolic potash (250 c.c., 5%) and refluxed for 30 minutes. After partial removal of the solvent and dilution with water and subsequent extraction with ether, 2-methylcyclohexenyl carbinol was isolated by distillation; yield 13 g., b.p. 73-76°/1 mm., n_D^{20} 1.4933. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 10.8. C₈H₁₄O requires C, 76.1; H, 11.1 per cent). It showed colour reaction with tetranitromethane, indicating the presence of unsaturation. The substance (0.254 g.) in presence of platinum oxide (0.008 g.) in methanol (50 c.c.) on complete hydrogenation absorbed 41 c.c. of hydrogen; calc. for C₈H₁₄O $\sqrt{1} = 44.9$ c.c.

1-Methyl-Δ²-cyclohexenylmethyl Bromide (XXII).—The above carbinol (20 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (200 c.c.) and anhydrous pyridine (20 c.c.) in a three-necked flask. PBr₃ (20 g.) was then added dropwise at 0° with mechanical stirring. The mixture was left at room temperature for 48 hours by which time it had developed a light brown colour. After heating for another 1 hour on the water-

bath it was decomposed with ice, further acidified with HCl and the bromide taken up in ether and isolated in the usual way; b.p. 67-70°/1 mm., yield 16 g. It was not analytically pure, as a small amount of the parent alcohol was retained as an impurity. However, as this did not interfere with the ultimate objective, further purification was not attempted.

11:12-Dimethyl- $\Delta^{3:4}$ -dodecahydrophenanthrene (XI).—The contents of three-necked flask fitted with mechanical stirring and containing clean sodium (10 g.) and dry toluene (20 c.c.) were boiled in an oil-bath. The impure bromide (13 g.) was carefully added from a dropping funnel during 5 minutes and the boiling and stirring continued for another 30 minutes. After cooling, the toluene solution of the diene was removed by decantation; the residue in the flask was washed two or three times with fresh toluene, the combined extract filtered, the solvent removed under reduced pressure and the diene collected by fractionation through a small column; b.p. 100°-115°/1 mm., yield 7.1 g. (any unchanged alcohol present in the bromide was eliminated at this stage as the sodio derivative. The formation of any ether by interaction of the bromide and the sodio derivative was not very pronounced as indicated by the ultimate purity of the desired phenanthrenoid). The entire amount of the diene, without further purification, was then cyclised by heating with mechanical stirring for 2 to 3 hours at 150°-160° with syrupy phosphoric acid (60 c.c., *d* 1.75). The hydrophenanthrene compound was then isolated as on the previous occasion and purified by repeated distillation over sodium, yield 2.9 g., b.p. 108-111°/1 mm., viscous oil, n_D^{25} , 1.5253. It was identical in all respects with the product obtained through route I. (Found: C, 87.61; H, 11.74. $C_{16}H_{26}$ requires C, 88.0; H, 12.0 per cent). The hydrophenanthrene (0.500 g.) in presence of platinum oxide (61 mg.) in methanol (70 c.c.) absorbed 51 c.c. of hydrogen; calc. for $C_{16}H_{26}$, $\sqrt{1} = 53.5$ c.c. This indicated that the cyclisation was complete. The structure of the cyclised product was further confirmed by dehydrogenation with selenium and isolation of phenanthrene, m.p. 100°; picrate, m.p. 144° and mixed m.p.

1-Methyl-2-acetyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene (XXIII).—Methylcyclohexene was prepared by dehydration of *O*-methylcyclohexanol with phosphoric acid and purified by fractional distillation, b.p. 105-108°. Methylcyclohexene (76 g.) and acetyl chloride (50 g.) in presence of stannic chloride in CS_2 furnished methylacetylcyclohexene (35 g.), b.p. 80°-90°/11 mm. .

Preparation of (XXVI) or (XXVII).—Potassium isopropoxide, prepared from molecular potassium (12 g.) and isopropyl alcohol (63 c.c.), was taken in a three-necked flask fitted with condenser, mechanical stirrer, guard tube and covered with anhydrous pyridine (120 c.c.). A mixture of *O*-methylcyclohexanone (24 g.) and methylacetylcyclohexene (30 g.) was slowly added with stirring. The mixture, which after leaving at room temperature for 24 hours had developed a light red colour, was heated on the water-bath for 6 to 7 hours, cooled, diluted with water, acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 and extracted with ether. The extract after usual processing by washing with dilute H_2SO_4 , bicarbonate, etc. was carefully fractionated through a small column. The phenanthrenoid compound distilled at 160°-175° (mostly at 170°/1 mm.), yield 9 g. It was a viscous material and did not form any semi-

carbazone. (Found: C, 82.0; H, 10.3. $C_{16}H_{24}O$ requires C, 82.7; H, 10.4 per cent). Slight discrepancy in carbon was probably due to a trace of impurity, removal of which was not attempted for fear of loss. Light absorption in alcohol (0.0002107 M): λ_{max} 239 m μ (log ϵ , 3.77), typical of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone.

β -Ketovaleric ester was prepared according to the method of Cook and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 391) from ethylmagnesium iodide and ethyl cyanoacetate and decomposition of the reaction product in the usual way. Ethyl iodide (250 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (70 g.) yielded the keto-ester (50-55 g.), b.p. 78°/11 mm.

Mannich Base (XXX).—The bases were prepared by following the original method of Mannich (*loc. cit.*) which was much superior to that of Robinson (*loc. cit.*).

2-Keto-1-methyl- $\Delta^{1,9}$ -octalene (XXXI & XXXII).—The methiodide obtained from the Mannich base (30 g.) in alcohol (100 c.c.) was mixed with the sodio derivative of β -ketovaleric ester, obtained from the ester (30 g.), absolute alcohol (210 c.c.) and sodium (4.8 g.), and refluxed on the water-bath for 7 hours. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, the residue was taken up in ether, washed successively with dilute HCl, water and dried and the contents fractionated, using a small column. The crude keto-octalene distilled at 90°-100°/0.5 mm., yield 10 g. A minor higher boiling fraction, b.p. 100°-150°/0.5 mm. (4 g.), which was composed of the β -keto ester (XXXIa), also furnished a little more of the keto-octalene on alkaline hydrolysis. The material was purified through its semicarbazone. The crude ketone (15 g.) produced from alcohol pure (plates) semicarbazone (15.5 g.), m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 8.62; N, 19.67. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.66; N, 19.0 per cent). Light absorption in alcohol (0.0000117 M): λ_{max} , 271 m μ (log ϵ , 4.16). The mother-liquor was preserved for the isolation of the semicarbazone of (XXXI).

For the isolation of the pure (XXXII), the semicarbazone was decomposed in the usual way by heating with $N-H_2SO_4$ for 10 to 15 minutes on the water-bath and the liberated ketone isolated and worked up; b.p. 110°-12°/3 mm., viscous oil with a camphor-like odour, yield 9 g., n_D^{25} 1.5326. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 9.96. $C_{11}H_{16}O$ requires C, 80.44; H, 9.82 per cent). Light absorption in alcohol (0.0000757 M): λ_{max} 246 m μ (log ϵ , 4.16).

The mother-liquor, left after separation of the first semicarbazone, on concentration and cooling furnished the semicarbazone of (XXXI) which on recrystallisation melted at 188°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 8.9; N, 18.9. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.66; N, 18.9 per cent). This semicarbazone can be better isolated by subjecting the keto-octalene mixture to treatment with $MgMeI$ which preferentially reacted with (XXXII). The reaction product on treatment with semicarbazide hydrochloride furnished the semicarbazone of (XXXI) which had remained unattacked (0.8 g. of pure semicarbazone from 5.0 g. of the ketone). The free ketone was obtained as in the previous case by decomposition with H_2SO_4 ; b.p. 70-72°/0.1 mm.

(Found: C, 79.90; H, 10.22. $C_{11}H_{16}O$ requires C, 80.44; H, 9.82 per cent). λ_{max} (alcohol), 248 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.94).

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